

ISic0140

I.Sicily inscription 0140

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D̄(is) [M(anibus)]
2. Can[inia]
3. Doḡ[ata]
4. viḡ(it) an(nis) [---]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To the Shades of the Underworld. Can[inia] Do[nata?] lived [...] years...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175705

EDR 077927

EDCS 8900405

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0527

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 59

Bivona, L 1975-1976. Nuove iscrizioni di Termini Imerese (Palermo). *Atti della Accademia di Scienze, Lettere a Arti di Palermo*. Ser.4, vol.35: 531-558. At 551 no.16 tav.8

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